

Executive summary CONSIGN D3

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Medicines use in pregnant women with COVID-19 and their effects

In the current COVID-19 pandemic, pregnant women are also infected with the SARS-CoV-2 virus and being treated for COVID-19 disease and its complications. The CONSIGN project is funded by the European Medicines Agency (EMA) (specific contract 04 implementing framework contract No EMA//28/PE, Lot 4) to be prepared for situations where questions arise regarding the impact of medicine used for COVID-19 during pregnancy on the mother and the unborn child and to inform policies on COVID-19 vaccination.

Given the changes to the cardiopulmonary and immune systems during pregnancy, pregnant women are at increased risk for severe COVID-19¹. Already in June 2020, the US Centers for Disease Control and Prevention reported that pregnant women with COVID-19 were more likely to be hospitalized and at increased risk for intensive care unit (ICU) admission and receipt of mechanical ventilation compared with non-pregnant women of reproductive age².

The World Association of Perinatal Medicine Working Group on COVID-19, with data from Europe, the US, South America, Asia and Australia reported a 0.8% rate of mortality and a 11.1% rate of ICU admissions among infected pregnant women; vertical transmission was negligible³. Recommendations about COVID-19 vaccines differ across jurisdictions and in many countries, pregnant women are often advised against it due to missing data on safety and efficacy during pregnancy. Given that pregnant women are excluded from these trials, it is important to assess the current safety profile of these drugs in pregnancy.

According to the WHO COVID-19, BMJ COVID-19 Hub, JAMA Network COVID-19, The Lancet COVID-19 Resource Center, New England Journal of Medicine COVID-19, and CMAJ COVID-19 registered trials, these medications include dexamethasone, interferon, heparins, angiotensin-receptor blockers (ARB), chloroquine, hydroxychloroquine, azithromycin, oseltamivir, and HIV medications⁴.

Recent COVID-19 management guidelines for the general population published by the National Institute of Health (NIH) updated on May 24th 2021, propose a disease severity-based management. For high-risk outpatients with mild to moderate COVID-19, SARS-CoV-2 neutralizing antibodies (bamlanivimab + etesevimab or casirivimab + imdevimab) are available through emergency use authorization accorded by the Food and Drug Administration (USFDA). For hospitalized patients that require oxygen support, remdesivir, dexamethasone, alone or in combination, are recommended through the USFDA. The most

¹ Mor G, Cardenas I. The immune system in pregnancy: a unique complexity. *Am J Reprod Immunol* 2010;63:425–33. pmid:20367629

² Ellington S, Strid P, Tong VT, Woodworth K, Galang RR, Zambrano LD, et al. Characteristics of Women of Reproductive Age with Laboratory-Confirmed SARS-CoV-2 Infection by Pregnancy Status—United States, January 22–June 7, 2020. *MMWR Morb Mortal Wkly Rep* 2020;69:769–75. pmid:32584795

³ COVID WWGo. Maternal and perinatal outcomes of pregnant women with SARS-CoV-2 infection. *Ultrasound Obstet Gynecol* 2021;57:232–41. pmid:32926494

⁴ Bérard A, Sheehy O, Zhao J-P, Vinet E, Quach C, Kassai B, et al. (2021) Available medications used as potential therapeutics for COVID-19: What are the known safety profiles in pregnancy. *PLoS ONE* 16(5): e0251746. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0251746>

severely ill patients requiring high flow oxygen support or invasive ventilation can be treated with dexamethasone alone or in association with remdesivir, with the possibility to add tocilizumab through the USFDA.

Chloroquine or hydroxychloroquine, with or without azithromycin, lopinavir-ritonavir and other antivirals as well as ivermectin have not been proven to be effective and thus are no longer recommended.

Information on the utilisation of COVID-19 treatments in pregnancy is still scarce. A preprint publication by Lai et al showed that data extracted in September 2020 revealed, that the ten most common inpatient treatments in the USA were systemic corticosteroids (29.6%), enoxaparin (24.0%), immunoglobulins (21.4%), famotidine (20.9%), azithromycin (18.1%), heparin (15.8%), ceftriaxone (7.9%), aspirin (7.0%), hydroxychloroquine (5.4%) and amoxicillin (3.5%).

To reply to the EMA needs and generate knowledge about the use and effects of medicines use in COVID-19 pregnancies we established a collaboration across many countries and several ongoing networks: IMI-ConcePTION, EU PE & PV, COVI-PREG and INOSS.

This deliverable comprises:

- 1) Data on medication utilisation in COVID-19 affected pregnancies from COVI-PREG (n=1,946), INOSS (n=927) and 5 electronic health care data sources in four European countries (capturing 2,022 COVID-19 pregnancies). Data from COVI-PREG and INOSS capture in hospital/clinic prescribing. Data from electronic health care data capture outpatient dispensings of prescriptions in primary and secondary (outpatient) care.
- 2) Interim analysis of INOSS data on maternal, obstetric and neonatal outcome in COVID-19 diagnosed pregnant women
- 3) Final analysis of COVI-PREG data on maternal, obstetric and neonatal outcomes in COVID-19 diagnosed pregnant women and the association with medicines use

Medication use during COVID-19 trimester of pregnancy (EHR data)

Five Data Access Providers (DAP) from four European countries (Italy, Norway, Spain and Wales) participated in this first study, which included all women who were pregnant at the start of the pandemic (01/03/2020) or became pregnant thereafter. Pregnancies were split in trimesters and medicines use was assessed per trimester. Data was obtained from prescribed or dispensed prescriptions in the primary care or outpatient setting, covering a period from June 2019 up to the end of data availability.

A total of 2,022 pregnant women had a recorded diagnosis of COVID-19 or a positive test. Figure 1 shows the distribution over time. In Italy-Tuscany (IT-ARS) and in the Aragon data source in Spain (ES-IACS) ongoing pregnancies could be identified. In other data sources pregnancies could only be identified if they had been concluded by the time of data extraction, which favors inclusion of third trimester COVID-19 exposed pregnancies (figure 2). In general, very few 1st trimester exposed pregnancies were included. In the second wave, most first trimester exposed pregnancies were from IACS in Spain and ARS in Italy.

Figure 1: Number (y-axis) included pregnancies by month of COVID-19 infection

Figure 2: Percentage of COVID-19 affected pregnancies by trimester of pregnancy and month of diagnosis (green shades: 3rd trimester, red-pink shades: 2nd trimester and blue shades: first trimester)

Anti-thrombotic agents (B01)

Among trimesters with a positive test or diagnosis of COVID-19, anti-thrombotic agents were the most commonly dispensed drug category of all 19 classes we examined.

In ARS - Italy and IACS- Spain, FISABIO-Spain, there was approximately a threefold increase in the prevalence of use of anti-thrombotic agents, compared to use in trimesters without a COVID-19 diagnosis.

In the IACS data source, approximately half of the 144 women who contracted COVID-19 during their second trimester were dispensed a prescription for an antithrombotic agent (B01), as were approximately a third of the 177 women in their third trimester. For those who contracted COVID-19 in the first or second trimester of their pregnancy, rates of use in the third trimester

were considerably higher than those who were in the third trimester of a pregnancy without a COVID-19 infection (13.7%, 95% CI: 8.0 to 19.4 vs. 7.4%, 95% CI: 6.8 to 8.0).

IT-ARS showed a similar pattern: a three-fold increase in prevalence when COVID-19 occurred.

In contrast, there was no increase in the dispensing of medication from this drug category in the SAIL data source from Wales, which also included pregnancies during second wave.

Antivirals (J05)

There was no increase in the prevalence of antiviral use during trimesters in which COVID-19 was diagnosed. In fact, across all data sources, less than ten pregnant women with COVID-19 were dispensed an antiviral medication during the trimester when they received a positive COVID-19 diagnosis.

Antibacterials (J01)

Antibacterial use was highest in Italy and Spain during pregnancy, independent of COVID-19. There was a tendency to a greater use of antibacterials during trimesters when a COVID-19 positive test or diagnosis was recorded compared to those without COVID-19, few of these increases were statistically significant given the wider confidence intervals in the prevalence estimates of the former group.

Analgesics (N02)

In the two Spanish databases (FISABIO-HSRU and IACS) high rates of analgesic use were observed compared with the other data sources. This may true in Spain but an artifact of reimbursement models in other countries (paracetamol is mostly OTC and not recorded in many countries). Prevalence rates of analgesics in trimesters with a COVID-19 diagnosis were two to three times higher compared to those trimesters without COVID-19.

Corticosteroids (H02)

There was a tendency towards a higher prevalence of use in trimesters with a COVID-19 diagnosis compared to the same trimester without COVID-19, but numbers were low.

Use in ARS was twice as high in first trimesters with COVID-19 compared to those without (6.8 %, 95% CI: 3.2 - 10.4 vs. 2.4%, 95% CI: 2.2 - 2.6); while use in the second trimester was three times higher (6.5%, 95% CI: 3.2 - 9.7 vs. 1.7%, 95% CI: 1.6 - 1.9). There was no difference between third trimesters with and without a COVID-19 diagnosis.

Medication use and outcomes in COVI-PREG

COVID-PREG collected data in a structured REDCAP database from all women who were suspected to have COVID-19 during pregnancy and visited a participating clinic. Women were followed from inclusion until the moment of delivery.

A total of 2352 eligible patients were exported from the REDCap online database from March 25th, 2020 to June 1st, 2021, from 35 countries across the world.

Of these, 1964 patients were included in the analysis after excluding untested patients (n=174), and those who tested negative or had unknown results (n=388).

Figure 3: Number of inclusions per week overall, in Switzerland, France and Spain (Top 3 of countries that have included the most patients).

The mean age of included pregnant subjects was 32 years old with an interquartile range (IQR) of 28-35. The majority was white (1050/1964; 53,5%) and the median body mass index at enrolment was 26.5 kg/m² (IQR 23 – 30.5). Women included were nulliparous in 32.6% (640/1964) and 18% (364/1964) of all women had at least one previous caesarean section.

Prevalence of pulmonary disease was 3.1% (60/1964), cardiac disease 1.4% (38/1964), hypertensive disease 2.7% (53/1964) and pre-existing diabetes 1.8% (36/1964). Singleton pregnancies represented 96.8% (1902/1964). Gestational diabetes was the most common ongoing pregnancy complication: 9.6% (189/1964) of patients and preeclampsia was diagnosed before exposure in 1.9% (37/1964).

A proportion of 11.4% (223/1964), 23.5% (462/1964) and 63.8% (1254/1964) of pregnant women were infected by SARS-CoV-2 in the first, second and third trimester respectively.

Among pregnant women who tested positive for SARS-CoV-2 during pregnancy, 10.4% (205/1964) had at least one COVID-19 related medicine for a total of 303 prescriptions.

Antibiotics were most frequently used (8.6%), followed by corticosteroids (3.2%), antivirals (2%), hydroxychloroquine (1.4%), anti-interleukin-6 (0.2%) and immunoglobulin (0.1%). Amongst antibacterials, azithromycin was most frequently used followed by amoxicillin/clavulanic acid and ceftriaxone. The most frequently used antivirals were lopinavir/ritonavir (13), oseltamivir (13) and remdesivir (10). While the most frequently used corticosteroids were: dexamethasone (39) and methylprednisolone (12). The only AntiIL-6 recorded was tocilizumab. COVI-PREG did not collect information on anti-thrombotics since the data collection tool was prepared at the beginning of the pandemic.

Prescriptions were very strongly related to COVID-19 severity, as expected (table 1). The severity of disease was divided into 5 levels as stated in Table 1. The proportion of patients receiving at least one COVID-19 related medicine was 3.2% (49/1510), 23.3% (84/360), 63.6% (28/44), 93.0% (40/43) and 57.1% (4/7) for COVID-19 infection severity level 1, level 2, level 3, level 4 and level 5 respectively

(Severity levels based on WHO criteria). Antibiotics were the most frequently prescribed medication class across all levels of severity.

Table 1: Description of COVID-19 medicines use among SARS-CoV-2 positive pregnant women by levels of infection severity

MEDICINES	LEVEL 1 = any SARS-CoV-2 diagnosis			Level 2 = hospitalisation			Level 3 = ICU admission			Level 4 = ARDS			Level 5 = maternal death							
	n	total	%	95% CI	n	total	%	95% CI	n	total	%	95% CI	n	total	%	95% CI				
	1510	/ 1964	76,9%		360	/ 1964	18,3%		44	/ 1964	2,2%		43	/ 1964	2,2%		7	/ 1964	0,4%	
ANY MEDICATION	49	/ 1530	3,2%	2,4 - 4,27	84	/ 360	23,3%	19,1 - 28,1	28	/ 44	63,6%	47,8 - 77,6	40	/ 43	93,0%	80,9 - 98,5	4	/ 7	57,1%	18,4 - 90,1
ANTIBIOTICS	45	/ 1530	3,0%	2,2 - 3,97	64	/ 360	17,8%	14,0 - 22,1	21	/ 44	47,7%	32,5 - 63,3	36	/ 43	83,7%	69,3 - 93,2	3	/ 7	42,9%	9,9 - 81,6
ANTIVIRALS	4	/ 1530	0,3%	0,1 - 0,68	16	/ 360	4,4%	2,6 - 7,1	6	/ 44	13,6%	5,2 - 27,4	10	/ 43	23,3%	11,8 - 38,6	3	/ 7	42,9%	9,9 - 81,6
HCO	5	/ 1530	0,3%	0,1 - 0,8	9	/ 360	2,5%	1,1 - 4,7	6	/ 44	13,6%	5,2 - 27,4	6	/ 43	14,0%	5,3 - 27,9	1	/ 7	14,3%	0,4 - 57,9
CORTICOSTEROIDS	1	/ 1530	0,1%	0,0 - 0,4	23	/ 360	6,4%	4,1 - 9,4	13	/ 44	29,5%	16,8 - 45,2	23	/ 43	53,5%	37,7 - 68,8	2	/ 7	28,6%	3,7 - 71,0
ANTI-IL6	0	/ 1530	0,0%	0,0 - 0,24	0	/ 360	0,0%	0,0 - 1,0	2	/ 44	4,5%	0,6 - 15,5	1	/ 43	2,3%	0,1 - 12,3	1	/ 7	14,3%	0,4 - 57,9
IMMUNOGLOBULIN	0	/ 1530	0,0%	0,0 - 0,2	0	/ 360	0,0%	0,0 - 1,0	0	/ 44	0,0%	0,0 - 8,0	2	/ 43	4,7%	0,6 - 15,8	0	/ 7	0,0%	0,0 - 41,0

* ICU: intensive care unit; ** ARDS: Acute respiratory distress syndrome

Association between medicines use and outcomes

A total of 1253 patients were included in the analysis that aimed to associate medicines with pregnancy outcomes. From the initial 2352 pregnant patients suspected of SARS-CoV-2 infection, 174 patients were excluded because they were not tested and 338 patients were excluded due to an unknown or negative PCR SARS-CoV-2 test. Ongoing pregnancies (n=658) and pregnancies that did not reach the theoretical post term date of 42 weeks (n=53) were also excluded to avoid selection bias for preterm birth.

Among the 1253 pregnant patients who tested positive for SARS-CoV-2, 5.6% (70/1253) had a severe form of the disease (WHO level 3-5) with at least intensive care unit admission. Due to the strong relationship of medicines use with COVID-19 severity we stratified all analyses by severity and did not match on other criteria.

In the subset of severe patients (level 3-5), COVID-19 related medicine use was much higher than in non-severe patients, as expected.

The association we observed between medicines use and adverse maternal outcome, defined as severe COVID-19 is thus well explained by confounding by indication and not a causal effect of the medicines. Confounding by severity also has a strong effect in the study on pregnancy and neonatal outcomes as the severe form of the disease leads to a higher risk of adverse pregnancy and neonatal outcomes. The numbers in our analysis do not allow for adequate adjustment for all potential confounders, while stratifying by severity.

Based on the COVI-PREG data we can conclude that pregnant women with severe COVID-19 are more likely to receive COVID-19 related medication and also are more likely to have adverse pregnancy outcomes. Since the COVI-PREG data was limited in numbers, when stratifying by severity of COVID-19 no firm conclusion can be drawn on the effectiveness or risk of medicines use in COVID-19 exposed pregnancies.

Medication use and outcomes in INOSS data

INOSS is a regional/national population-based data collection system of hospitalized pregnancies with COVID-19. Structured data collection is conducted by all sites for all cases who were hospitalized and tested positive within 7 days prior or 2 days after hospitalization (inclusion criteria). INOSS sites collected information on medicines use in hospital and collected information on maternal and pregnancy outcomes after birth, independent of the location of birth.

This 2nd INOSS interim report included descriptive data of pregnancies with reported COVID-19 from 6 countries up until August 2020. A total of 2166 pregnancies positive for SARS-Cov-2 and admitted were reported, 927 of these pregnant women were admitted because of COVID-19 or were symptomatic, these 927 women constitute the study population.

The frequency of admission related to COVID-19 was highest in the UK and Nordic countries using the number of pregnancies in the area as the denominator.

The most frequently applied treatments in hospital for pregnant women who were admitted for COVID-19 were anti-bacterials (one third), steroids (5.6%) and antithrombotic treatment (8%). It was only in Italy that hydroxychloroquine was frequently used (58%); this treatment not used in other countries. Between country variation was high for treatment practices (?).

Amongst 927 pregnant women admitted to hospital due to COVID-19, the rates of ICU admission were relatively frequent (8.8%); so too were preterm births (17%) compared to the general pregnant population. Maternal death and the need for mechanical ventilation or ECMO were 0.8% and 4.4%, respectively.

Preliminary data on perinatal and neonatal outcomes showed that out of 813 deliveries 807 resulted in a livebirth. A relatively high proportion of neonates required NICU admission (19.4%). Six neonates had a congenital anomaly detected prior to discharge.

General conclusion

Our complementary data from the different data collection systems (outpatient prescribing, and in-patient) showed similar patterns although absolute rates differed.

Anti-bacterials, steroids and anti-thrombotic agents were used increasingly for COVID-19. Hydroxychloroquine was used very differently across countries. Use of antivirals was much lower than use of anti-bacterials.

We also show that severity of COVID-19 is very strongly associated with use of medicines. In any analysis on the effects of medicines use for COVID-19 and pregnancy outcomes, severity should be stratified for.

Estimating medicines benefits and risks will require careful analysis to deal with the very strong confounding by severity.